

CONCENTRATION OF MERCURY IN MEAT AND SLOVAK TRADITIONAL MEAT PRODUCTS*

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SUMMARY: Mercury contents have been determined by atomic absorption spectrometry in the Selected ham, Frankfurters, "Lovecka" salami, "Malokarpatska" salami. The highest concentration of mercury in raw materials (beef, pork, pork bacon) was beef. Increasing concentrations of mercury was found after the addition of additives, spices and curing compounds causing a threefold increase in the concentration of mercury in finished products. We found statistically significant differences ($P < 0.001$) in the concentration of mercury between the starting materials and the finished product.

Key words: mercury, meat, meat products, AAS.

INTRODUCTION

Meat and meat products are important for human diet in many parts of the world because they contribute to solve the global food problem and provide the well-known proteins, minerals, vitamins and trace element contents (Alturiqi et al., 2012). Contamination with heavy metals is a serious threat because of their toxicity, bioaccumulation and bio magnifications in the food chain (Demirezen et al., 2006). In recent years, much attention has been focused on the concentration of heavy metals in fish, and other foods in order check for those hazardous to human health (Alcaide-Castineira et al., 1995). Metals such as iron, copper, zinc and manganese are essential metals since play important role in biological system, whereas mercury, lead and cadmium are toxic, even in trace amounts. Lead, cadmium, mercury are among the main toxic metals which accumulative effect. The essential metals can also produce toxic effects at high concentrations (EC, 2001). Pastirma and sausage were analysed for heavy metals, their levels depend on factors such as environmental conditions, type of pasture and genetic characteristics of organisms (Demirezen and Aksoy, 2004). Foods may be contaminated by

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chemicals from many different sources (soil, sediment, water, air). Using different kinds of food (meat, dairy products, fish, vegetables and fruits), animals and human may be also contaminated with chemicals (Abou-Arab, 2001).

Mercury occurs as elemental mercury and as inorganic and organic compounds, all having different toxicological properties. Total mercury can be analysed in water, air and biological material (Massányi et al. 2003). The toxic properties of mercury vapour are due to mercury accumulation in the brain causing neurological signs. At high exposure levels, mercury tremor is seen accompanied by severe behavioural and personality changes, increased excitability, loss of memory and insomnia (Nordberg et al., 2007).

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the concentration of mercury in the traditional and popular meat products in Slovakia (selected ham and frankfurters, *Lovecka* and *Malokarpatska salami*) during the technological processing.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sampling was done so that the samples were representative that to have the average composition and characteristics of the goods from which they were collected. The collection sample during the manufacturing process was carried out under the following scheme.

“Selected ham” was sampled starting raw material (pork thigh), than samples homogenized meat with additives (salt and Sodium nitrite, Sodium pyrophosphate, sodium tripolyphosphate, Sodium Ascorbate). Finally, the actual sample of the finished product after heat treatment, cooling to 25°C and after drying in climates with $a_w = 0.95$. *“Frankfurters”* were sampled raw materials (beef, pork, pork bacon and emulsion of skin), then followed by homogenized samples with the addition of substances (salt, Sodium ascorbate, polyphosphates, ground pepper). *“Lovecka salami”* - were collected basic raw (beef, pork and pork bacon); than samples mixed meat with additives (salt, Sodium Ascorbate, Erythorbic acid, ground black pepper, sugar, garlic, starter culture) and finally the actual sample of the finished product after heat treatment, cooling to 25°C and drying in climates with $a_w = 0.95$. *“Malokarpatska salami”* - were collected basic raw (beef, pork and pork bacon); than samples mixed meat with additives (salt, spice extracts, Sodium Nitrite, highlighter flavor, Lactobacillus) and finally the actual sample of the finished product after heat treatment. The concentration of mercury was determined in a total of 45 samples of raw materials respectively finished product. Samples after collected were packed to plastic bags, and frozen (-18°C). Concentrations of total mercury in samples were measured with cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometer (Nippon Instrument Corporation MA-2). 30-50 mg of meat or homogenized meat samples and final products were used in the protocol. The material was not mineralized before the measurement and the analyses were performed with the wet weight (w/w) of the material. The samples were supplemented with two additives: additive M (Wako Pure Chemicals Industries Ltd. for NIC 286-61845) and additive B (Wako Pure Chemicals Industries Ltd. for 282- 98 62665) to minimize potential interferences. Limit of detection established for the whole procedure was 0.170 ng of total Hg. The accuracy of the method was checked against the certified reference material (BCR-463). Final results were given in ppb ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) for meat and other samples

We set the basic variation statistical values (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, maximum and minimum value). The significant differences

between means were calculated by a one way analysis of variance using Duncan's multiple range test at $P < 0.001$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concentrations of mercury in the selected ham are presented in Table 1. Mercury in the selected ham was present in the range of 5.231–1.159 ppb. The highest concentration was detected in finish product selected ham 6.236 ± 0.724 ppb. The lowest concentration of mercury was determined in samples of pork 1.159 ± 0.242 ppb. Results obtained in this study were lower than those obtained by Noël et al.(2011). They were quantified in 97% samples. The mean Hg concentrations in white meat ranged between 76 ppb for king crabs and 151 ppb for swimming crabs.

Table 1. Basic variation statistical characteristics of mercury concentration in the raw materials and final product Selected ham

	Selected ham		
	pork thigh/Hg	homogenized samples/Hg	finish product/Hg
$\bar{X}$	2.198 ^{***A, B}	6.108 ^{***A}	6.236 ^{***B}
SD	0.38	0.623	0.724
CV	17.34	10.20	11.61
SEM	0.14	0.220	0.256
MIN	1.65	4.89	4.98
Median	2.215	6.108	6.13
MAX	2.58	6.87	7.45

Legend: $\bar{X}$ - mean SD – standard deviation, CV(%) – coefficient of variation, MIN – minimum, MAX – maximum value, ^A pork thigh versus homogenized samples; ^B pork thigh versus finish product ^{***} $P < 0.001$

The concentrations of mercury were observed in the samples frankfurters starting from raw materials (beef, pork, pork bacon, emulsion skin), homogenized samples and finish product are as presented in Table 2. The highest concentration of Hg was found in the finish product (5.231 ± 0.720 ppb) and the lowest level was observed in the pork samples (1.159 ± 0.720 ppb). From raw materials was found the highest concentration of mercury in the beef (2.048ppb). Ingestion of contaminants with various environmental pollutants, especially heavy metals by animals causes deposition of residues in meat. Due to the grazing of cattle on contaminated soil, higher levels of metals have been found in beef (Sabir et al., 2003). In Nigeria, the main source of metals in chicken meat and meat of goat, sheep and beef arises from contamination of feed and drinking water (Akan et al., 2010). In animal food products one of the most important factors that influence the content of toxic metals in animal products is the life span of the animals. Animals with long life span such as horse, older cattle and game, can accumulate some inorganic contaminants (Lukáč and Massányi, 2011).

Table 2 Basic variation statistical characteristics of mercury concentration in the raw materials and final product Frankfurters

	Frankfurters					
	beef/Hg	pork/Hg	pork bacon/Hg	emulsion of skin/Hg	homogenized samples/Hg	finish product/Hg
$\bar{X}$	2.048 ^{***ABC}	1.159	1.459	4.61 ^{***A}	4.762 ^{***B}	5.231 ^{***C}
SD	0.835	0.242	0.289	0.836	0.954	0.720
CV	40.76	20.86	19.84	18.13	20.04	13.76
SEM	0.264	0.007	0.009	0.264	0.302	0.223
MIN	1.25	0.95	0.95	3.54	3.57	4.2
Median	1.55	1.0	1.5	4.68	4.715	5.231
MAX	3.27	1.54	1.89	6.15	6.54	6.51

Legend: $\bar{X}$ - mean, SD – standard deviation, CV(%) – coefficient of variation, MIN – minimum, MAX – maximum value, ^A beef versus emulsion of skin; ^B beef versus homogenized samples; ^C beef versus finish product ***P<0.001

The concentrations of mercury in the “Lovecka” salami are presented in Table 3. Hg levels ranged between 1.239±0.2251 ppb in the pork bacon, 1.787±0.2163 ppb in the pork, 2.334±0.2897 ppb in the beef, 6.986±1.342 in the homogenized samples and 7.463±1.438 ppb in the finish product. We found statistically significant differences (P<0.001) in the concentration of mercury between beef versus finish product; pork versus finish product; pork bacon versus finish product. Result of concentration of mercury in samples Malokarpatska salami are shown Table 4. From raw materials the highest concentrations of mercury had beef 2.751±1.095 ppb. The average concentration of mercury was higher in homogenized samples with addition additives and spices 6.159±1.530 ppb and finish product Malokarpatska salami 9.295±2.367 ppb. Significant differences at the significance level P<0.001 in the concentration of mercury between the raw materials and finished product. Endo et al. 2003 surveyed the total mercury levels in red meat. All concentrations in all red meats were present in the range 0.52– 0.54 ppb. Hg concentrations in the “Lovecka” salami exceeded level of the total mercury levels in red meat, the most popular cetacean products in Japan.

Table 3. Basic variation statistical characteristics of mercury concentration in the raw materials and final product “Lovecka” salami

	Lovecka salami				
	beef/Hg	pork/Hg	pork bacon/Hg	homogenized samples/Hg	finish product/Hg
$\bar{X}$	2.334 ^{***A}	1.787 ^{***B}	1.239 ^{***C}	6.986	7.463 ^{***ABC}
SD	0.2897	0.2163	0.2251	1.342	1.438
CV	12.41	12.10	18.17	19.21	19.27
SEM	0.1183	0.0883	0.0919	0.548	0.5872
MIN	1.858	1.458	0.851	5.489	5.231
Median	2.335	1.866	1.253	6.935	7.756
MAX	2.687	2.045	1.458	8.678	9.248

Legend: $\bar{X}$ - mean SD – standard deviation, CV(%) – coefficient of variation, MIN – minimum, MAX – maximum value, ^Abeef versus finish product; ^B pork versus finish product; ^Cpork bacon versus finish product ***P<0.001

Table 4. Basic variation statistical characteristics of mercury concentration in the raw materials and final product “Malokarpatska” salami

	Malokarpatska salami				
	Beef/Hg	Pork/Hg	Pork bacon/Hg	Mixed samples/Hg	Finish product/Hg
$\bar{X}$	2.751 ^{***A}	1.494 ^{***B}	1.364 ^{***C}	6.159	9.295 ^{***ABC}
SD	1.095	0.511	0.262	1.530	2.367
CV	39.82	34.17	19.21	24.85	25.47
SEM	0.346	0.1614	0.0828	0.484	0.749
MIN	1.25	1.05	0.98	2.58	7.15
Median	2.69	1.23	1.35	6.54	8.76
MAX	4.27	2.41	2.01	7.84	15.4

Legend: $\bar{X}$ - mean SD – standard deviation, CV(%) – coefficient of variation, MIN – minimum value, MAX – maximum value, ^A beef versus finish product; ^B pork versus finish product; ^C pork bacon versus finish product ^{***}P<0.001

According to the Codes of Alimentarium in the Slovak republic, the maximal admitted or contaminating mercury in meat and meat product is 0.05mg.kg⁻¹. In our analysis concentration of mercury in raw materials and finished products were below the permitted level of Hg. According Alturiqi and Albedair mercury contents of samples chicken's meat ranged between 0.009-0.015ppb. Hg concentrations obtained from this study were higher than the permitted mercury limit of study Alturiqi and Albedair. The levels estimated in our meat products are lower to those observed by Barreto et al. (2009) (160- 610 ppb in white meat products).

CONCLUSIONS

Results from this study show that mercury concentrations in Selected ham, Frankfurters, “Lovecka” salami, “Malokarpatska” salami were systematically below the maximum level of 0.05 mg.kg⁻¹. Their levels depend on factors such as environmental conditions. From the results of this study, finished products were found the highest significant levels of mercury and raw materials the lowest levels. Technological treatments are important for levels of mercury in meat products. Heavy metals transfer to animals and humans through the food chain JECFA, 2004. Technological process of processing meat can create a potential source of heavy metals in finish products.

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KONCENTRACIJA MERCURY-a U MESU I TRADICIONALNIM SLOVAČKIM PROIZVODIMA OD MESA

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Izvod

Sadržaj merkurijske je određena automatskom apsorpcionom spektrometrijom, u selektovanim šunkama, Frankfurterima, "Lovecka" salami i "Malokarpatska" salami. Najviša koncentracija merkurijske, u svežem materijalu, (junetina, svinjetina i svinjski bekon), ustanovljena je u junetini. Povećanje koncentracije merkurijske je ustanovljena posle dodavanja aditiva, što povećava koncentraciju merkurijske u gotovim proizvodima od mesa. Ovo povećanje koncentracije merkurijske, u gotovim proizvodima, u odnosu na sirovo meso, bila je statistički značajna ($P < 0.001$).

Ključne reči: mercury, meat, meat products, AAS.

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